

Supplementary materials for

Genome-wide signatures of convergent evolution in barnacle and mollusc phenotypes

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Supplementary Notes:

Supplementary Note 1. Genome assembly and annotation

Based on the genome sequencing data in the form of 49 Gb of Illumina paired-end reads (96×) and 57 Gb of PacBio long reads (112×, Supplementary Table S1), a high-quality genome of the stalked barnacle *C. mitella* was assembled. The assembled genome size was 512.06 Mb (Table 1), which was close to the size estimated by K-mer analysis (513.60 Mb, Supplementary Fig. S2). The assembly showed high continuity, with a contig N50 length of 3.22 Mb, which is among the longest for a crustacean assembly (Supplementary Table S2). The contigs of *C. mitella* were further anchored to 16 chromosomes using high-throughput chromosome conformation capture (Hi-C) sequencing data (277×, Fig. 2A). More than 93% of the contigs were anchored and the N50 length of the final chromosome-level genome assembly was 30.73 Mb (Table 1). The assembly showed high integrity and quality, based on benchmarking universal single-copy ortholog (BUSCO) analysis (94.74%) and unigenes from transcriptomes (91.82%) (Supplementary Fig. S3, Tables S3, S4).

Repeat annotation revealed that 33.44% of the *C. mitella* genome was composed of repetitive sequences, which was a lower percentage than that found in the genome of the acorn barnacle *A. amphitrite* (43.83%, Supplementary Table S5). *C. mitella* harbored more DNA transposons (5.91%), whereas *A. amphitrite* harbored more simple sequence repeats (3.54%). Among the identified DNA transposons, hAT (2.16%) and TcMar (1.04%) were the two most common transposon types, and most of these transposons expanded recently (Supplementary Fig. S4, S5).

Genome annotation combined gene evidence from homology-based prediction, *ab initio* prediction and transcriptome-based prediction methods. We predicted 13,364 protein-coding genes in the *C. mitella* genome, with an average length of 1,554 bp and an average of 7.32 exons per gene (Supplementary Table S6). BUSCO analysis indicated a high completeness (93.15%) of the annotated genes in *C. mitella*, which was comparable to or better than the completeness of many other reported crustacean genomes¹.

Supplementary Note 2. Phylogenetic analysis

Based on the 28 conserved single-copy orthologous genes among 16 arthropod species, a high consensus phylogenetic tree was constructed. The two barnacle species (*C. mitella* and *A. amphitrite*) was paraphyletic with malacostraceans and nested by other crustaceans (Fig. 2B). Then, we estimated the molecular clock and the divergence times using a combined analysis of the programs of r8s and RAxML². *C. mitella* is a stalked barnacle in the suborder Lepadomorpha, which is estimated to have diverged from the other major group of thoracican barnacles (sessile barnacles, Sessilia, represented by *A. amphitrite*) approximately 237 million years ago (MYA), just after the Permian-Triassic mass extinction event (~ 252 MYA). The thoracican barnacles are estimated to have diverged from other crustaceans approximately 521 MYA (Fig. 2B), close to the timing of the origin of molluscs (the Early Cambrian)³. In addition, molluscs started to exhibit mineralization at the dawn of the Cambrian Period⁴. This is consistent with the hypothesis that the biological mechanisms of biomineralization may have evolved at nearly the same time, as biomineralization is the most visible aspect of the so-called “Cambrian explosion”⁵. Therefore, the calcareous shells of barnacles and molluscs may have originated at the same time during the Cambrian.

Supplementary Note 3. Gene family expansion and contraction of the *C. mitella* genome

Gene family clustering was performed on the protein-coding genes of *C. mitella* and 15 additional arthropods, and the gene gain and loss events were identified along each branch of the phylogenetic tree. Functional enrichment analysis indicated that the expanded gene families of the two barnacle genomes were primarily enriched in KEGG terms of Cell adhesion molecules (CAMs), thiamine metabolism, inflammatory mediator regulation of transient receptor potential (TRP) channels, folate biosynthesis, neuroactive ligand-receptor interaction, phagosome, and so on (Fig. 2D, Supplementary Fig. S6). Cell adhesion molecules (CAMs) and proteins involved in adherens junctions and tight junctions might be very important for their unique sessile lifestyle. Thiamine is a B1 vitamin that is important in carbohydrate

metabolism and the normal activity of the nervous system⁶. TRP channels exhibit a unique response to temperature that mediates thermal tolerance and have been identified as diagnostic biomarkers of thermal stress in oysters⁷. Therefore, the expansion of these gene families may reflect the adaptive evolution of barnacles related to the shell formation, sessile lifestyle and inhabiting stressful intertidal zones.

Supplementary Note 4. Whole-genome duplication

Whole-genome duplication (WGD) is arguably the most sudden and massive change that a genome can experience in a single evolutionary event⁸. Currently, only a few groups of invertebrates, such as bdelloid rotifers, horseshoe crabs and house spiders, have been demonstrated to have undergone WGD⁸⁻¹⁰. Whereas, a potential diploidization event was reported in a single genus of parasitic barnacles¹¹. Some conserved developmental genes, such as *engrailed*, have also been reported to be duplicated in barnacles¹². This suggests that a WGD event might have occurred in the barnacle genome, but no further evidence has been presented to support this hypothesis.

First, a whole-genome synteny analysis was performed in the *C. mitella* genome, and 197 syntenic blocks covering at least 5 ordered paralogous genes were detected, which was comparable to findings in the horseshoe crab *Tachypleus tridentatus* (320 syntenic blocks), a species that has undergone three rounds of WGD^{13,14}. These syntenic blocks of paralogous genes are shared between chromosomes (e.g., Chr11 and Chr12), similar to the pattern found in the horseshoe crab but different from that in the oriental river prawn *Macrobrachium nipponense* (randomly distributed), a crustacean that is assumed to have undergone WGD¹⁵. The presence of such paralogous blocks throughout the genome suggests that the duplicated genes are the result of WGD, rather than independent duplications in which case the paralogous genes would be randomly distributed in the genome¹³.

More duplicated genes will be detected in genomes that have been copied once or multiple times. As expected, the barnacle genomes exhibited significantly more duplicated BUSCOs (25.66% on average) than other crustacean genomes (8.62% on

average, $P < 0.05$, Supplementary Fig. S3). To provide further insight into the nature of the genome at the gene level after the WGD event, we analyzed the Hox gene cluster in *C. mitella*. Ten conserved syntenic Hox genes and four miRNAs (miR-993, miR-10 and miR-iab-4/8) were present in the *C. mitella* genome, although *Hox3* and *Abd-A* were not present (Fig. 3B). The absence of *Abd-A* is associated with impaired development of the abdomen in barnacles¹⁶. However, we identified an incomplete segment of *Abd-A* located between *Ubx* and *Abd-B* that could not be transcribed and translated, suggesting the nonfunctionalization of this gene. In addition to the complete Hox gene cluster on Chr3, an additional small cluster including *Antp*, *Ubx* and two miRNAs (miR-993 and miR-10) was identified on Chr7, which may have been generated during the WGD event (Fig. 3B). Most of the genes duplicated via WGD are subsequently lost during evolution¹⁷. In the *C. mitella* genome, relics of WGD could be found in some other conserved gene clusters, but many of them had lost their second copies (Supplementary Fig. S8). This finding suggests that the WGD event might have taken place a long time ago.

To determine the timing of the WGD event, we calculated the distribution of the synonymous substitution rates (K_s) of paralogous gene groups in the genome of *C. mitella*. A peak at approximately $K_s = 0.8$ suggests the occurrence of a WGD, similar to that of *T. tridentatus* ($K_s = 1.1$, Fig. 3C). A K_s peak ($K_s = 0.6$) of orthologous genes between the two barnacle species (*C. mitella* versus *A. amphitrite*) was identified before the K_s peaks of the paralogous genes of *C. mitella* ($K_s = 0.8$) and *A. amphitrite* ($K_s = 1$). This result indicates that WGD might have occurred before the divergence of the thoracican barnacles (Lepadomorpha and Sessilia)¹⁸.

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Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Morphology of the stalked barnacle *C. mitella*. (A) Morphology of *C. mitella*. (B) Environment inhabited by *C. mitella*. Stalked barnacles, sessile barnacles and oysters coexist in the same environment.

Figure S2. K-mer distribution of the Illumina sequencing data. K-mer analysis estimated the genome size of *C. mitella* to be 513.60 Mb.

Figure S3. Core gene coverage of the genomes of barnacles and other crustacean relatives. The database used for BUSCO assessment was composed of 1066 BUSCOs of Arthropoda.

Figure S4. Substitution rate distribution of repeats in the *C. mitella* and *A. amphitrite* genomes.

The substitution rates were calculated between the genomic and repeat consensus sequences using RepeatMasker.

Figure S5. Substitution rate distribution of DNA transposons in the *C. mitella* genome.

The substitution rates were calculated between the genomic and repeat consensus sequences using RepeatMasker. hAT, TcMar and CMC-EnSpm were the three most common transposons in the *C. mitella* genome. hAT and TcMar expanded recently, and CMC-EnSpm showed ancient expansion.

Figure S6. Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) enrichment analysis of the expanded gene families in the two barnacle genomes (*C. mitella* and *A. amphitrite*).

The expansion of the gene families was calculated using CAFÉ by comparing differences in cluster sizes between each of the current species and their respective ancestors. The top 20 KEGG pathways under significant enrichment of the expanded gene families are shown in the plot.

Figure S8. Representative conserved gene clusters with second or multiple copies in the *C. mitella* genome.

(A) The conserved gene cluster “Rax-Hbn-Otp” is incomplete. Only “Rax-Otp” exists on Ctg22, and the other two Rax and Otp gene copies exist on different contigs (Ctg43 and Ctg44). (B) Conserved paralogous “*NotchL* loci”. (C) Conserved paralogous “*Pde4L* loci”. (D) Conserved paralogous “*FasIL* loci”.

Figure S9. Phylogenetic tree of carbonic anhydrases. (A) Phylogenetic tree of carbonic anhydrases (CAs) of molluscs and crustaceans. Specific expanded CAs are shown against purple for molluscs, and green for barnacles. The motifs calculated with the MEME suite, which are labeled with different colors based on the domain type, are shown in the exterior circle of the phylogenetic tree. (B) The expression levels of CAs in the nauplius and cyprid stages of barnacles. Barnacles start to form calcareous shells during the cyprid stage. (C) Tandem duplication of CAs in the genomes of *C. mitella* and *A. amphitrite*.

Figure S12. Phylogenetic tree of cuticle proteins. Branches of the phylogenetic tree with different backgrounds indicate genes from different species. The exterior circle around the phylogenetic tree displays the classification of the various types of cuticle proteins.

Figure S13. Phylogenetic tree of endocuticle structural glycoproteins. The motifs calculated with the MEME suite, which are labeled with different colors based on the domain type, are shown in the exterior circle around the phylogenetic tree.

Stalk barnacle

Acorn barnacle

Figure S14. Morphology of barnacle shells. The lower figure shows a cross-section of the upper figure (yellow line). In barnacle shells, the external portion has a massive microstructure consisting of randomly oriented crystals, while the interior portion is organized in mineral layers separated by thin organic sheets

Fig. S15. The phylogenetic tree of glutathione S-transferase (GST). Red and blue labels in the phylogenetic tree represent genes of barnacles and intertidal molluscs, respectively. GST Delta and Mu were specifically expanded in the barnacle genomes.

Fig. S16. Tandem duplication of cytochrome P450 (CYP450). CYP450 genes were tandemly duplicated in the *C. mitella* genome. There were nine copies of two tandemly duplicated CYP450 genes in the genome that were not shown in this figure.

Figure S17. The expression patterns of heat shock protein 20 of *C. mitella* during air exposure.

C, L, M and H at the bottom represent the samples collected underwater (control) and at low, middle and high sites from the water level, respectively. The expression levels are normalized for each gene.

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Summary of the genome sequencing clean data of *Capitulum mitella*.*

Sequencing platform	Illumina	PacBio	Hi-C
Size of library	500 bp	20 Kb	500 Kb
Number of Reads	164,836,636 * 2	4,203,896	712110824 * 2
Average length (bp)	150	13,643	100
Total Bases (bp)	49,450,990,800	57,355,949,854	142,422,164,800
Sequencing Depth (X)	~96.28	~111.67	~277.30

* The *C. mitella* genome size was estimated about 513.60 Mb.

Table S2. Summary of the genome assembly of the sequenced crustaceans.

Species	Assembly length	Contig N50	Scaffold N50	Accession No.
<i>Capitulum mitella</i>	512,057,600	3,223,513	30,732,139	This study
<i>Amphibalanus amphitrite</i>	610,566,118	240,779	458,238	PRJNA549550
<i>Armadillidium vulgare</i>	1,717,747,144	38,359	51,088	PRJNA501402
<i>Daphnia pulex</i>	158,607,408	47,461	642,089	PRJEB14656
<i>Eriocheir sinensis</i>	1,293,881,449	26,045	150,053	PRJNA636904
<i>Eulimnadia texana</i>	120,535,642	18,070,303		PRJNA352082
<i>Eurytemora affinis</i>	386,487,637	23,141	252,275	PRJNA423276
<i>Fenneropenaeus chinensis</i>	1,554,960,535	58,996	28,916,617	PRJNA627295
<i>Homarus americanus</i>	2,292,059,586	133,311	759,644	PRJNA655509
<i>Hyalella azteca</i>	596,627,768	5,445	987,977	PRJNA342675
<i>Lepas anserifera</i>	756,396,212	671,058		PRJNA678024
<i>Lepidurus apus</i>	90,320,486	43,471		PRJNA417576
<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i>	1,618,026,442	57,650	31,296,514	PRJNA508983
<i>Macrobrachium nipponense</i>	1,976,961,095	267,348	83,001,933	PRJNA646023
<i>Parhyale hawaiensis</i>	2,921,140,205	4,003	69,178	PRJNA306836
<i>Penaeus monodon</i>	2,000,783,471	45,084	44,862,054	PRJNA679074
<i>Pollicipes pollicipes</i>	761,780,280	109,725	47,009,503	PRJNA624368
<i>Portunus trituberculatus</i>	1,004,084,517	4,109,061	21,793,880	PRJNA555262
<i>Procambarus virginalis</i>	1,627,847,010	745	39,275	PRJNA356499
<i>Tigriopus californicus</i>	177,715,849	37,992	298,012	PRJNA237968

Table S3. Unigene coverage on the *C. mitella* genome.

Unigenes	Number	Percent
Total unigenes	150,511	100%
Matched unigenes	138,206	91.82%
90% in one scaffold	121,284	80.58%
50% in one scaffold	135,655	90.12%

Table S4. Core gene estimation for *C. mitella* assembly using BUSCO.

	Number	Percentage (%)
Complete BUSCOs	971	91.09
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	824	77.30
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	147	13.79
Fragmented BUSCOs	39	3.65
Missing BUSCOs	56	5.25
Total BUSCO groups searched	1066	100

Table S5. Statistics of repetitive elements for the *C. mitella* genome.

Species	<i>C. mitella</i>	<i>A. amphitrite</i>
Genome length	512,057,600	610,566,118
Repeat length	171236128	268882291
Repeat percent	33.44%	43.83%
SINEs	0.13%	0.00%
LINEs	1.94%	2.98%
LTR elements:	1.59%	1.99%
DNA elements:	5.91%	0.97%
Unclassified:	23.50%	34.00%
Total interspersed repeats:	33.07%	39.93%
Simple repeats:	0.59%	3.54%
Satellites:	0.16%	0.03%
Low complexity:	0.01%	0.46%

Table S6. Statistics of the annotated gene features for *C. mitella*.

Species	<i>Capitulum mitella</i>
Gene number	13,364
Gene density (gene_number/100kb)	2.61
Gene average length	1,554 bp
Exon number per Gene	7.32
Intron number per Gene	6.32
Exon average length (bp)	212.0 bp
Intron average length (bp)	2137.3
Genome GC percent%	49.93%
Exon GC percent%	67.63%
Intergenic region average length	13,356.5bp

Table S7. KEGG enrichment of the genes retained from Whole Genome Duplication.

Pathway ID	KEGG class*	Pathway	Pvalue	Qvalue
ko04360	O	Axon guidance	1.72E-12	2.73E-10
ko04010	E	MAPK signaling pathway	5.40E-10	5.71E-08
ko04015	E	Rap1 signaling pathway	2.58E-08	2.01E-06
ko04520	C	Adherens junction	3.18E-08	2.01E-06
ko04014	E	Ras signaling pathway	3.45E-07	1.82E-05
ko04080	E	Neuroactive ligand-receptor interaction	1.12E-06	4.62E-05
ko04514	E	Cell adhesion molecules (CAMs)	1.17E-06	4.62E-05
ko04625	O	C-type lectin receptor signaling pathway	1.33E-06	4.69E-05
ko04910	O	Insulin signaling pathway	2.79E-06	8.08E-05
ko04660	O	T cell receptor signaling pathway	2.80E-06	8.08E-05
ko04390	E	Hippo signaling pathway	1.30E-05	3.44E-04
ko04310	E	Wnt signaling pathway	1.65E-05	3.73E-04
ko04391	E	Hippo signaling pathway -fly	1.81E-05	3.82E-04
ko04361	O	Axon regeneration	2.24E-05	4.45E-04
ko04062	O	Chemokine signaling pathway	5.42E-05	1.01E-03
ko04151	E	PI3K-Akt signaling pathway	0.0001959	3.45E-03
ko04740	O	Olfactory transduction	0.0002742	4.57E-03
ko04810	C	Regulation of actin cytoskeleton	0.0004585	6.61E-03
ko04658	O	Th1 and Th2 cell differentiation	0.0005546	7.32E-03
ko04722	O	Neurotrophin signaling pathway	0.0006453	7.87E-03
ko04728	O	Dopaminergic synapse	0.000679	7.97E-03
ko04150	E	mTOR signaling pathway	0.0008154	8.78E-03
ko04916	O	Melanogenesis	0.0008237	8.78E-03
ko04530	C	Tight junction	0.0008305	8.78E-03

* KEGG classes include organismal systems (O), environmental information processing (E) and cellular processes (C).

Table S8. Summary of gene families involved in intertidal zone adaptation.*

Gene family	Aamp	Cmit	Cgig	Cvir	Sglo	Mph	Myes	Obim	Hdis	Tcal	Lvan	Avul
HSP10/Cpn10	2	1	1	3	4	1	3	1	0	1	0	1
HSP20	6	14	19	19	14	14	6	7	11	15	27	10
HSP40/DnaJ	42	29	51	62	46	40	46	34	23	40	30	68
HSP60/Cpn60	19	11	16	17	17	15	13	13	10	12	11	11
HSP70	27	16	111	172	112	86	63	12	15	14	17	94
HSP90	3	2	3	7	4	3	3	5	3	2	5	4
SOD	14	8	11	14	8	10	8	4	4	6	3	5
CAT	3	3	3	2	2	1	2	1	0	1	1	2
PRX	7	5	3	5	4	4	4	4	2	5	5	4
GPx	5	4	9	8	6	9	9	4	5	4	10	7
GST delta	13	5	1	2	1	1	0	0	1	5	12	4
GST mu	6	5	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	14
P450	88	65	133	111	113	234	113	60	108	55	55	165
Tret1	45	26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	16	27
FREP	92	25	203	158	580	204	60	13	84	17	38	25
IAP	2	1	48	22	45	14	13	1	7	4	3	4

*The abbreviation of genes include heat shock protein (HSP), chaperonin (Cpn), chaperone protein DnaJ (DnaJ), superoxide dismutase (SOD); catalase (CAT); peroxiredoxin (PRX), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), glutathione S-transferase (GST), cytochrome P450 (P450), facilitated trehalose transporter 1 (Tret1), fibrinogen-related domain containing protein (FREP), inhibitor of apoptosis protein (IAP). The included species are *Amphibalanus amphitrite* (Aamp), *C. mitella* (Cmit), *Crassostrea gigas* (Cgig), *Crassostrea virginica* (Cvir), *Saccostrea glomerata* (Sglo), *Modiolus philippinarum* (Mphi), *Mizuhopecten yessoensis* (Myes), *Octopus bimaculoides* (Obim), *Tigriopus californicus* (Tcal), *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Lvan) and *Armadillidium vulgare* (Avul).

Table S9. GO enrichment of the differentially expressed genes during high vs. low tide.

	GO ID	Description	pvalue	p.adjust
CC	GO:0005576	extracellular region	5.05E-09	3.88E-07
MF	GO:0008234	cysteine-type peptidase activity	2.35E-10	4.13E-08
	GO:0008061	chitin binding	1.15E-09	1.02E-07
	GO:0004197	cysteine-type endopeptidase activity	2.43E-09	1.43E-07
	GO:0042302	structural constituent of cuticle	2.49E-05	0.001093
	GO:0070011	peptidase activity, acting on L-amino acid peptides	0.000257	0.009053
	GO:0008233	peptidase activity	0.000409	0.012008
	GO:0016787	hydrolase activity	0.001398	0.035156
	GO:0030414	peptidase inhibitor activity	0.001834	0.035858
	GO:0061134	peptidase regulator activity	0.001834	0.035858
	BP	GO:0006030	chitin metabolic process	1.36E-09
GO:1901071		glucosamine-containing compound metabolic process	1.36E-09	2.53E-07
GO:0006040		amino sugar metabolic process	1.74E-09	2.53E-07
GO:0006022		aminoglycan metabolic process	3.13E-09	3.42E-07
GO:1901135		carbohydrate derivative metabolic process	9.57E-05	0.008365
GO:0006508		proteolysis	0.000195	0.014214